

WASCC-E-010

INTEGRATING SAR DATA AND DNDC BIOGEOCHEMICAL MODEL FOR
ESTIMATING THE METHANE EMISSION FROM RICE FIELDS

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ABSTRACT

Methane emissions from rice fields have long been recognized as one of the major contributors to anthropogenic sources of greenhouse gas emissions. Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) imagery, especially where cloud cover restricts the use of optical imagery. Parameterized classification with multi-temporal features derived from regularly acquired, C-band, VV, and VH polarized Sentinel-1A SAR imagery was used for mapping rice areas. A fully automated processing chain in MAPscape-Rice software was used to convert the multi-temporal SAR data into terrain-geocoded σ^0 values, which included strip mosaicking, co-registration of images acquired with the same observation geometry and mode, time-series speckle filtering, terrain geocoding, radiometric calibration, and normalization. Further Anisotropic non-linear diffusion (ANLD) filtering was done to smoothen homogeneous targets while enhancing the difference between neighboring areas. The rice area map was generated using a rule-based classifier approach utilizing parameterization with a classification accuracy of 91.5 percent and a kappa score of 0.83 respectively. The total classified rice area in the Cauvery Delta Zone was 467134 ha in 2018. DNDC model estimated the methane emission rate of 42.13 kg ha⁻¹ season⁻¹ with a total methane emission of 19.86 Gg in the Cauvery Delta Zone during 2018. The overall agreement between DNDC-based methane emission and field observation was found to be 79.1 percent. The higher percent of agreement between spatially estimated methane emission and observed values indicated the suitability of Remote Sensing coupled with the DNDC model in the estimation of methane emission for regional or national level GHG monitoring.

Keywords: Rice, Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR), Sentinel 1A, DNDC, Methane emission.